

FEATURES OF THE FIELD OF TRANSLATION STUDIES

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Abstract. *In this article says about translating and interpreter's activity.*

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Today, the Uzbek people differ from other peoples in their culture of communication and communicative approach, and we are proud of this. No nation can understand another nation unless it deeply understands itself. Political, economic, scientific and cultural cooperation between different peoples is expanding throughout the world; these relations cannot be imagined without translation. Introduce the translation process and the quality of the result, provide information about translation theory, and direct an independent translation. texts in 2 languages. It is to teach important aspects of translation that should be paid attention to from the point of view of international conferences, negotiations and media sources. During the translation process, it is important to pay attention and know the following. from foreign languages into Uzbek. The science and technology of translation being a horse with knowledge of the history of literature, the history of translation studies and their main periods, linguistics - translation - extralinguistics; in-depth understanding of grammatical, lexical, semantic, stylistic and phraseological issues of translation from eastern and western languages into Uzbek and from Uzbek into eastern and Gharbi languages;

- have information about the features of translation types and the scope of their use;
- Grammatical problems of translation into the native language, compatibility and incompatibility of the same sentence systems in Eastern, Western and Uzbek languages; stylistic problems of translation into the native language;
- must have an understanding of the peculiarities of translating literary, political, social, historical and popular science texts, as well as the skills of collecting the necessary information from the Internet and translation skills based on a scientific approach.
- have a complete understanding of the pragmatic problems of translation, types of translation, lexical alternative, basic methods used in translation; problems that have arisen in translation studies, as well as disputes and opinions of scientists about translation, studying the experience of ancient translators and researchers, studying the main issues about discussions in the field of translation studies, the ability to objectively evaluate and analyze translation, written, oral, and acquire the skills to study the main features of visual translation;
- conduct scientific research in the field of translation studies, be able to apply the experience and methods created by great translators in the history of translation to modern translation, be able to apply theoretical knowledge in practice, conduct research in this area of translation studies, apply the acquired theoretical knowledge when translating works, study, consciously choose linguistic means when translating, take into account the lexical, semantic,

phraseological and stylistic features of texts in the native language and foreign languages, as well as be able to use them;

Theoretical and practical foundations and vocabulary of the language being studied, translation of scientific and fiction literature into this language, studied Eastern and Western languages and the process of their development, historical linguistic aspects of this language, basics of translation practice, text translation, it is necessary to master the principles of simultaneous translation, consecutive translation, literary translation, terminological translation, written translation, media translation, visual translation, teaching skills and speech culture, have skills such as literary translation work and exemplary service, intensive teaching. languages taught and service organization, simultaneous, visual, consecutive interpretation at international conferences, international use of information technologies in practice and must be able to apply professional standards, modern pedagogical and information technologies. These aspects, mastered in translation studies, serve as the basis for activities. Also, studying examples of world literature and the history of their translation when analyzing the translation of these works helps to understand translation skills and solve some theoretical questions and problems.

The history of translation began in ancient times. We see that at all times translation served the interests of the development of science and friendship of peoples. Translated literature developed along with original written literature and became its integral part. Since ancient times, peoples speaking different languages communicated with each other through translators. It was difficult to manage without a translator in trade, diplomatic relations and cultural relations. style of literary language and language. The differences cannot be ignored. According to V. Belinsky, “any translation is intended for people who do not know the original language.”: “The first basic condition of any translation is knowledge of the object of translation, which consists in fluent command of two languages. Know what the collapsing work is about. Requirements for the content, idea and quality of “translated” works changed in each period. Translation is the re-expression of an idea expressed orally or in writing in a particular language using other linguistic means. The main feature of translation is that it is a creative process of reconstruction using other linguistic means, it is the art of words. The idea expressed in the original must be fully, clearly and effectively reflected in the translation; the translation must comply with the norms of the target language. In the process of translation, two situations arise: the thing being translated must first be understood, defined and interpreted. This happens in the native language - elements of translation arise. Secondly, for translation it is necessary to find appropriate means of expression in the language into which the work is translated. However, when translating from one language to another, two common situations occur. other: The goal of the translator is to fully acquaint the reader or listener who does not know the original language with the content of the text or oral speech. To translate means to accurately and completely express what is expressed by language in another language. “The translation process consists of 3 stages: 1) Perception of the original; 2) Interpretation of the original copy; 3) Repetition of the original. Understanding the original by a translator, who captures a work with the aim of translating it into his own language, occurs in 3 stages: At the first stage, the text is perceived literally, philologically. At this stage, translation errors may occur: mixing a word from another language with a word that sounds the same; falling into the trap of false equivalents in related languages, misattribution of context, misunderstanding the meaning of some specific words; not understanding the author's content, at the second stage attention is paid to methodological factors; A reader who has read the text correctly also

understands the stylistic factors of linguistic expressiveness, mood, tone, and a tendency to dryly describe the story. The translator must determine and examine how the author achieves the relevant result. Translation requires a conscious attitude towards the book with higher demands than ordinary reading; The third stage - from understanding the stylistic and semantic content of certain linguistic means, the translator moves on to understanding the artistic integrity of the work, phenomenon, features, relationship to artistic reality, and the author's ideological intention. more difficult - artistic reality created by the author. To fully understand, a translator needs to have a wide range of powers of observation. In order to fully grasp and understand the original, the translator must have the ability to represent, based on an analysis of the achievements and shortcomings of the centuries-old history of translation, the science of translation studies, which has developed certain principles and rules, is aimed at providing general recommendations to a translator who solves specific problems personally. The components of the science of translation are: History of translation. Translation theory. Criticism of translation.

The history of translation studies the history of the emergence and development of translated literature.

The translation theory is a philological science that studies the laws of translation and the principles of translation.

The task of translation theory is based on the achievements of translation practice, to identify patterns between the original-translation relationship, to generalize and streamline established rules and turn them into guidelines for use in subsequent translations.

The practical significance of translation theory is to satisfy the need for scientifically based principles that do not allow each linguist to create his own translation principles.

The scientific significance of translation theory lies in the fact that as a result of problems caused by the "collision" of two linguistic means in the translation process, opportunities for further development of the language open up. Translation criticism controls the translation process, evaluates published works, and helps improve the quality of translations. It solves practical and organizational issues of translation work and develops in interaction with literary criticism. A translator translating a work for the first time faces difficulties and opportunities - he translates the way he wants, with visible meanings. The next translator will look for different words and special expressions so as not to be similar. The history of Uzbek translation is rich in different styles, genres, themes, and directions. These translations reflect the unique characteristics of each era. A generalization of the history of translation in Uzbekistan from a scientific point of view, an in-depth analysis and identification of the stages and basic principles of the history of translation will be the subject of separate scientific research. The process of establishing translation theory as an independent science began in the 20s of the 20th century. Valuable comments on translations of classic writers are important. When studying the process of formation of the principles of translation and the formation of the theory of translation as a science, the practice of translation from one language to another is studied and general situations in science are generalized. Translation is only about language. The exact content and aesthetic qualities of a word cannot replace each other. The existing theoretical literature on translation is devoted to analyzing the problem of what can be translated and what can be translated. At the level of available sources, we present our thoughts and opinions about the history of literary translation after the 20s of the twentieth century. Creating such a history, which is necessary at the moment, is the subject of independent scientific work and requires special research. He consults a dictionary that does not

use the word or phrase because it is not in the dictionary. not a translator. Based on general rules, the translator personally solves specific problems that arise during the translation of a particular work. One of the common features of translations before the 19th century is that most of the authors and translators of original historical works were poets and writers, and also translated works of fiction, history, and philosophy. The translators did not specialize in any particular field or specific genres. as now, he also translated historical works and philosophical books. Until the 19th century, not a single publishing house or organization in Uzbekistan planned or published translation work based on the needs and requests of the people. Some changes were made when copying them. Handwritten copies of translated works vary. In old translations, some scientific, medical, philosophical works, dictionaries are given in verse. This situation often arises when translating historical works. Many translators lived with the people and spent all their strength and talents on filling their spiritual lives with meaning. It is the deep knowledge, broad worldview and extensive life experience of the translator that ensure the success of the translation. A translator, who knows the nature and living language of the people well, in order to increase it, looks for words and phrases that are not in dictionaries. liveliness, colloquialism and clarity of the translated work. This is his creativity in the field of language. The spiritual closeness of the author and translator, mutual understanding and commonality of styles is a true achievement of any translation. It is the deep knowledge, broad worldview and rich life experience of the translator that are the main factors ensuring the success of the translation.

Conclusion. A translator who knows the nature and living language of the people well looks for words that are not in dictionaries in order to increase the liveliness, nationality and understandability of the translation work. language, what a real achievement of translation.

REFERENCES

1. Salomov G. Introduction to the theory of translation - Tashkent, 1978. P. 18. A. Navoi, 17.-T, 2001. v. 12.)
2. From the book "Language and Translation" (T, publishing house "Fan", 1966)
3. Current issues in literary translation, Tashkent: "Fan", 1977.
4. Salomov G. Translation skills. Tashkent: "Fan", 1979.